

Copper(II), Nickel(II), Cobalt(II), Manganese(II), Zinc(II) and Iron(III) Complexes of γ -(3-carboxy-4-hydroxy- benzoyl)butanoic Acid

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Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Mn^{II} , Zn^{II} and Fe^{III} complexes of γ -(3-carboxy-4-hydroxybenzoyl)butanoic acid have been synthesised and characterised on the basis of analytical, spectral, thermal and magnetic measurements. Various ligand ($10 D_q$) and nephelauxetic parameters (B and β) have been evaluated for octahedral Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes. Tetrahedral structures are suggested for Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} while octahedral and square planar structures are suggested for Fe^{III} and Cu^{II} complexes. The infrared spectra reveal that (i) the aromatic carboxylic group is deprotonated while the phenolic group hydrogen remains intact and, (ii) metal ion is bonded to both the carboxylic oxygen and phenolic oxygen.

SALICYLATE complexes of many metals including those of transition metals have been reported by a number of workers^{1,2}, but most of these studies have been carried out in solution. Some workers have studied salicylato-complexes in the solid state but conflicting results have been reported³⁻⁶. However, there is no mention in the literature of any reaction between γ -(3-carboxy-4-hydroxybenzoyl)butanoic acid, γ -(CHB)BA and transition metals. The present paper describes the preparation and characterisation of transition metal complexes of γ -(CHB)BA. In the formation of metal complexes of various derivatives of salicylic acid, the phenolic group dissociates and which plays an important part in the complex formation⁶. In the present investigation we found that the carboxylic proton dissociates while the phenolic group remains intact.

Experimental

Preparation of γ -(3-carboxy-4-hydroxybenzoyl)butanoic acid: Polyphosphoric acid (50 g) was added to a mixture of salicylic acid (69 g, 0.05 mol) and glutaric acid (9.9 g, 0.075 mol) and then heated at 130° for 6 h. The solid obtained was added to ice-cold water, filtered and washed with hot water. It was purified by dissolving in NaOH solution (10%) and reprecipitated with ice-cold HCl (10%) as a brown coloured compound (78.3%), m.p. 160°. It is soluble in alcohol.

Preparation of complexes: A general procedure was adopted to synthesise the complexes. Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Mn^{II} , Zn^{II} and Fe^{III} chloride (0.01 mol, 20 ml) was mixed with ligand in absolute alcohol (0.02 mol, 50 ml; 0.03 mol, 75 ml for Fe^{III} complex). The resulting precipitates obtained

by addition of sodium acetate were washed with hot water and ethanol and dried in vacuum desiccator.

Elemental analyses and physical measurements: Carbon and hydrogen analyses were performed by Coleman carbon hydrogen analyser. The metal contents of the complexes were determined according to standard procedures⁷. The analytical data are given in Table 1. Room temperature magnetic susceptibilities were measured by Gouy method using $Hg[Co(NCS)_4]$ as the calibrant. Magnetic moments were corrected for the temperature-independent paramagnetism. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded in UR-10 spectrophotometer. Diffuse reflectance spectra in the solid state were obtained from a Beckman DU spectrophotometer using MgO as reference. TG data were obtained from an assembly capable of producing temperature upto 800° with a heating rate of 10° min⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complexes support the proposed formulations. All the complexes are stable under normal conditions and insoluble in common organic solvents. The percentage loss in weight (found, calcd.) on heating above 150° for Ni^{II} (6.0, 6.01%) and Co^{II} (5.51, 6.01%) complexes indicate the presence of two coordinated water molecules⁸. The formation of respective metal oxides occurs at 600-700°. The decomposition temperatures are given in Table 1.

The most important ir bands of diagnostic value and their tentative assignments for the ligand and its complexes are listed in Table 2. In the carboxylato-complexes symmetrical (ν_s) and asymmetrical (ν_a) stretching modes of COO group

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA OF COMPLEXES

Complex	Decomp. temp. °C	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)		
			C	H	M
γ (CHB)BA	300		57.68 (57.14)	5.36 (4.79)	
Cu[γ (CHB)BA] ₂	250	1.9	50.56 (50.93)	4.10 (3.91)	11.55 (11.22)
Ni[γ (CHB)BA.H ₂ O] ₂	250	3.1	48.20 (48.77)	4.41 (4.38)	10.07 (9.83)
Co[γ (CHB)BA.H ₂ O] ₂	200	5.1	48.31 (48.25)	4.22 (4.38)	10.21 (9.86)
Mn[γ (CHB)BA] ₂	275	6.2	51.80 (51.71)	4.00 (3.97)	9.50 (9.27)
Fe[γ (CHB)BA] ₂	250	5.9	53.85 (53.41)	4.31 (4.10)	7.38 (6.89)
Zn[γ (CHB)BA] ₂	200	diamagnetic	51.11 (50.76)	4.21 (3.90)	11.93 (11.51)

TABLE 2—SPECTRAL CHARACTERISTICS OF COMPLEXES

Complex	Frequency cm ⁻¹	Transition	COO		M-O
			ν_{as}	ν_s	
γ (CHB)BA			1680	1620	
Cu[γ (CHB)BA] ₂	20000 15384	² B _{1g} → ² E _g ² B _{1g} → ² B _{2g}	1600	1440	530
Ni[γ (CHB)BA.H ₂ O] ₂	25000 20000 11000	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (P) ³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (F) ³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{2g} (F)	1610	1460	530
Co[γ (CHB)BA.H ₂ O] ₂	20833 8474	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (P) ⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{2g}	1600	1460	550
Mn[γ (CHB)BA] ₂	22220 21052 19230	⁶ A ₁ → ⁶ E ₁ ⁴ A ₁ (G) ⁶ A ₁ → ⁶ T ₂ (G) ⁶ A ₁ → ⁶ T ₁ (G)	1600	1450	560
Fe[γ (CHB)BA] ₂	20000	⁶ A _{1g} → ⁶ T _{1g} (F)	1600	1450	540
Zn[γ (CHB)BA] ₂	—		1600	1450	500

are of much importance since their positions and separation can help in determining the type of bonding. It has been accepted⁹ that the covalent character of M-O increases with an increase in $\Delta \nu$ COO. In present investigation aromatic COO stretching frequencies in γ -(CHB)BA have been found to be sensitive to coordination to the metal. In all the complexes, the ν_s COO and ν_{as} COO modes are observed at 1450 and 1600 cm⁻¹, respectively. The $\Delta \nu$ COO value is about 150 cm⁻¹ which indicates the covalent character of M-O bond. In ligand ν_{C-O} of aromatic COOH is observed at 1670 cm⁻¹ and aliphatic COOH is observed at 1700 cm⁻¹. The 1700 cm⁻¹ band does not shift on complexation which indicates aliphatic COOH is free in complexes. A strong band at 1220 cm⁻¹ in ligand is assigned to ν_{C-O} of phenolic group which shifts to 1150 cm⁻¹ on complexation¹⁰.

The broad band observed at \sim 3300 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to the absorption of the coordinated OH group¹¹. All the complexes show weak band at 580-600 cm⁻¹ due to M-O bond¹². The ir spectra suggest that the coordinated carboxylic group acts as monodentate.

The copper(II) complex under study has a magnetic moment value of 1.9 B.M. The magnetic moment of the nickel complex 3.1 B.M. is in the expected range of divalent nickel in an octahedral field¹³. The Co^{II} complex exhibits magnetic moment 5.1 B.M. indicating it to be high spin with three unpaired electrons and having octahedral stereochemistry¹⁴. 6.2 B.M. value for the Mn^{II} complex is as expected for five unpaired electrons¹⁵. The iron(III) complex has 5.4 B.M. value which is lower than expected for high spin complex. The

low value of magnetic moment can be interpreted in terms of antiferromagnetic behaviour¹⁶.

The diffuse reflectance spectra (Table 2) of Cu^{II} complex shows two bands and together with magnetic moment value suggest a square planar geometry¹⁷. In the case of Ni^{II} complex the transitions are characteristic of octahedral stereochemistry¹⁸. The ratio ν_3/ν_1 (1 : 80) lies in the range required for Ni^{II} octahedral complexes¹⁹. In high spin Co^{II} complexes the experimentally observed spin-allowed transitions in increasing order of energy are ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$, and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ and are denoted as ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 , respectively. The reflectance spectra of Co^{II} complex shows two bands which are assigned to octahedral stereochemistry²⁰. Using $10D_q$ (9660 cm^{-1}) and B (903 cm^{-1}), ν_3 was calculated. The ratio ν_3 (calcd.)/ ν_1 (found) is 2.14 as required for octahedral Co^{II} complexes. The value of B for the free gaseous ion, 972 cm^{-1} , is used to calculate the value for nephelauxetic ratio, β (0.93). In Mn^{II} complexes the intensity of the electronic transitions from the ground state (6S) to the states of four-fold multiplicity are very weak²¹. Since Mn^{II} has a d^5 configuration the same type of energy level diagram applies whether the metal ion is surrounded by tetrahedral or octahedral environment. Here, the Mn^{II} complex exhibits bands which are assigned to tetrahedral stereochemistry²². The Fe^{III} complex shows broad peak at 20000 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ transition for octahedral stereochemistry²³. The Zn^{II} complex is diamagnetic and may have tetrahedral structure.

In view of these observations the following structures may be assigned to the complexes.

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